

Judean/Yehudite Colony at Elephantine (Persian period)

also known as "Jewish Community at Elephantine (Persian period)"

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Entry tags: Jewish Traditions, Abrahamic, Religious Group

Standard encyclopedic introductions to a religious community generally begin with information on the group's name, origins, and overview of its membership. This information, however, is highly debated among experts. Therefore, the current introduction begins with the points on which scholars are broadly in agreement. During the fifth century BCE, on the island of Elephantine (an island in the Nile near Aswan) officials of the Persian Empire oversaw a multi-ethnic /multi-cultural colony which centered on a military garrison patrolling the empire's southern border. In the early twentieth century several Aramaic papyri connected to this garrison were presented to British amateur archeologists by local Egyptians. Since then, many more documents—papyri and ostraca—have been brought to light either on antiquities markets or through excavation. Most of these documents belong to the fifth century BCE (Van der Toorn, *Becoming Diaspora Jews*, 3-8). The Aramaic documents from Elephantine which include official and personal correspondence, administrative documents, contracts, as well as a copy of the Words of Ahiqar and an Aramaic version of the Behistun inscription, shed light on a diverse community. Within the documents one can find individuals and groups described by a wide-range of gentilic adjectives as well as references to Egyptian, Persian, and Syro-Canaanite deities. Among those personal and group descriptors are a number of references to "yhwdyn" (singular "yhwdy"). Some documents refer to the "yhwdy garrison in Elephantine." Among the deities, there are references to "YHW," the deity of the biblical Israel and Judah described in the Hebrew Bible (there spelled YHWH). The documents even indicate that there was a temple to YHW. How to properly describe this group of yhwdyn who worship YHW at his temple is a matter of debate. With respect to the group's name, scholars translate yhwdyn variously as Judean, Yehudites, and Jews reflecting their positions on the group's origins, ethnicity in the ancient world, and when Judaism (or, more broadly, religion) emerges as a category. Concerning the question of the group's origins, the documents from Elephantine only hint at potential answers. Scholars generally recognize that the group came from the Levant, but precisely where they came from in that region, when they came to upper Egypt, and under what conditions is a matter of conjecture. Regarding the religion of the community at Elephantine, scholars again are left to piece together the evidence. One highly fragmentary document, TAD A4.1 or "the Passover Papyrus" seems to be concerned with timing around a festival. Some scholars have connected this to the Feast of Unleavened Bread and Passover despite neither being mentioned in the papyrus. Other documents reference a temple to YHW and sacrifices offered there. Some of these documents are addressed to the governor of Yehud. This raises questions about the centralization of the cult of YHWH in Jerusalem. Documents from Elephantine also reveal that the priests of the Egyptian god Khnum with the support of a certain Persian official destroyed the temple to YHW calling into question the harmony between various groups at Elephantine.

Date Range: 500 BCE - 399 BCE

Region: Elephantine

Region tags: Egypt, Elephantine

Elephantine is an island west of Aswan in the Nile, downstream from the first cataract.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: B. Porten and A. Yardeni, *Textbook of Aramaic Documents from Ancient Egypt*. Vol. 1 (=A): Letters (Jerusalem: The Hebrew University, 1986); Vol. 2 (=B): Contracts (Jerusalem: The Hebrew University, 1989); Vol. 3 (=C): Literature, Accounts, Lists (Jerusalem: The Hebrew University, 1993); Vol. 4 (=D): Ostraca & Assorted Inscriptions (Jerusalem: The Hebrew University, 1999).
- Source 2: B. Porten, *The Archives from Elephantine: The Life of an Ancient Jewish Colony* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1968)
- Source 3: A. Azzoni, *The Private Lives of Women in Persian Egypt* (Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 2013)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.dainst.org/en/projekt/-/project-display/25953?p_r_p_1690909578_redirectURL=%2Fsuchen%3Fp_p_id%3D3%26p_p_lifecycle%3D0%26p_p_state%3Dmaximized%26p_p_mode%3Dview%26_3_%252Fproject-display%252F63449%26_3_keywords%3DElephantine%26_3_assetCategoryTitles%3D%26_3_entryClassName%3D
Notes: This is the site for the ongoing excavations at Elephantine which explores the millennia of history on the island, including the relatively brief Persian Period.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.bibleodyssey.org/en/people/related-articles/worshipping-yahweh-outside-the-province-of-yehud>
- Source 1 Description: This is a broader discussion about Yahweh worship outside of ancient Israel and Judah.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://elephantine.smb.museum/?lang=en>

– Source 1 Description: Currently there is an effort underway to make texts from several periods of Elephantine's history available online at this site. The goals of this project have not yet been realized.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.smb.museum/museen-einrichtungen/aegyptisches-museum-und-papyrussammlung/sammeln-forschen/forschung/erc-projekt-elephantine-lokalisierung-von-4000-jahren-kulturgeschichte-texte-und-schriften-der-insel-elephantine-in-aegypten/?L=1>

– Source 2 Description: This is the description of the project aimed at creating a database of texts from Elephantine.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: There are at least 15 other groups in contact with the Judeans on Elephantine as known from inscriptions from Elephantine and the nearby Syene (modern day Aswan). Judeans seem to have been primarily in contact with Persians, Egyptians and Arameans. (See Becking, "The Other Groups that Were")

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Documents suggest that there were disputes between Judeans and non-Judeans (e.g. TAD B2.2); however, there is nothing to suggest that these disputes were on the basis of any ethnic or religious identity with the exception of the temple destruction mentioned in the question regarding violent contact outside of the sample religion.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: There is an instance of an individual appealing to YHW alongside of Egyptian god Khnumm at Elephantine which suggests some level of pluralism (e.g. TAD D7.21). A Judean woman also swears by Sati (TAD B2.8).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Evidence is limited on the scale of violent clashes with other groups. There is one violent incident recorded in two letters (TAD A4.5 and A4.7). The priests of Khnum (spelled "Khnum" in the papyri) evidently bribed Vidranga, the Persian official for Elephantine to allow them to remove the temple to YHW and stop up the community's well. It should be noted that this incident is only recorded from the Judean perspective.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: It would seem that the community has official political support from the Persian authorities based upon the official role Hananiah plays vis-a-vis Persian authorities. (See Kratz, "Judean Ambassadors and the Making of Jewish Identity"). There also seems to be an amicable relationship between leadership in the Judean community at Elephantine and the governors of Samaria and Judah both of which were under Persian governance. It is unclear whether or not the governors of Samaria and Judah had any meaningful authority over the colony.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A series of letters and memoranda between community leaders in Elephantine and the

Persian officials in Judah and Samaria suggest that the community in Elephantine expected or hoped for support from this Persian leadership (alongside of the religious leadership in Judah and Samaria). (TAD A4.7-A4.10)

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The exact leadership structure among the Judean community at Elephantine is opaque. Jedaniah/Yedaniah is a figure mentioned in several documents (eg TAD A4.1, A4.3, A4.7, etc.) from Elephantine. He is mentioned in TAD A4.7 with "his colleagues the priests." It is unclear whether Jedaniah is a priest. Hananiah is another potential leader figure whose role is ambiguous in the letters. In TAD A4.1 he seems to be standing between Darius II and the community commenting on a (religious?) festival. TAD A4.10 mention five "property owners" who seem to be in a leadership role advocating for the rebuilding of a temple to YHW. None of them have religious titles. (See Granerød, Dimensions of Yahwism, 32-41)

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The documents found at Elephantine do not contain a legal or religious code (however several contracts indicate some sort of personal law existed). The links between the documents at Elephantine and biblical legal material should not be overdetermined.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A lack of adequate data prevents scholars from knowing the population of Judeans at Elephantine; however, some scholars have attempted to estimate a number based upon administrative data, particularly TAD C3.15, a collection account and others use an understanding of ancient military organization as the Judean community was connected to a military garrison. Estimates range from 500-700 to 2500-3000+ Judeans. (Granerød 2016)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Possibly 10%, the number is speculative (Granerød 2016).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Field doesn't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Documents from Elephantine indicate that there was a first temple to YHW that likely predated Cambyses' entrance to Egypt (TAD A4.7.13-14), but that temple was destroyed c. 410 BCE. Few archaeological remains from that temple have been discovered. The archaeological record indicates there was a temple to YHW. It is likely these remains belong to a second, rebuilt temple. Documents from Elephantine indicate that the community requested to rebuild this temple, but they do not clearly indicate this was done (A legal document, TAD B3.12, dated 402 BCE that references the

temple might suggest one was rebuilt. It could also be referencing the memory of a temple.) (See Granerød, Dimensions of Yahwism, 81-104).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no mention of afterlife in documents from Elephantine; however, absence of evidence does not mean evidence of absence. One might expect that the community came into contact with notions of the afterlife based upon their location in Egypt.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: One sarcophagus with Aramaic writing possibly dating to the Persian period and possibly belonging to a Judean was found at Aswan. The evidence is very limited on burial practices. (W. Kornfeld, "Aramaische Sarkophage in Assuan," Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde des Morgenlandes 61 (1967))

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: While I am slightly uncomfortable with the word "supreme," sources at Elephantine indicate YHW was at least the preferred god for the Judeans at Elephantine given the documents' focus on the temple, the number of times YHW is invoked in the documents as well as the yahwistic theophoric personal names.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "YHW the god of heaven" is a common way to refer to YHW at Elephantine.

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
 - Notes: The copy of the Behistun inscription at Elephantine indicates that the community at least received propaganda stating that Darius I was legitimate "by the favor of Ahuramazda." This suggests the community was familiar with a "sacral kingship," whether or not they adopted the viewpoint of the propaganda (Granderød, Dimensions of Yahwism, 227-244).
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: It would seem god has some knowledge of this world if god's blessings for individuals in this world are requested (TAD A4.7)
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: It would seem god has some causal efficacy in this world if god's blessings, strength, happiness, welfare, and longlife for individuals in this world are requested (TAD A4.7).
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: It is unclear what the purpose of food/animal offerings are.
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Judeans certainly acknowledged other gods and invoked them in oaths. Whether or not they "worshipped" other gods is an open question, but one might suspect they did given the level of contact between Judeans and others.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

Notes: The pantheon at Elephantine is impressive with gods whose origins can be traced to several areas of the ancient Near East. I am not personally familiar with the origin stories of each of those deities to comment on whether they were "previously human spirits." I would suspect the average Judean at Elephantine would likewise not have this breadth of knowledge.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: In the previous question, YHW was treated as the "supreme high god." This stance might be controversial. Other deities known from Elephantine (ie AnatYHW, Sati, Khnum, etc.) "non-human supernatural beings" here.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Other deities are acknowledged in Judean documents including AnathYHW, Sati (Egyptian goddess), Herem, Herembethel, Khnum, Anuket. They were familiar with the Egyptian pantheon and gods generally associated with the Levant.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: "Organization" is a difficult word to use in relation to the Pantheons at Elephantine. YHW does seem to be the supreme deity. Several deities are recognized. How they fit into the Judeans' understanding of an organized divine world is an open question.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: God's are invoked in making oaths; however, little is known about how Judeans conceived of monitoring.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Invoking gods in oaths would suggest they are involved in monitoring prosocial norms.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Oaths are directed at property crimes, but it is unclear whether the deity cares about the oath or the property.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear to what extent the narrative/proverbial text "The Words of Ahiqar" found at Elephantine reveals what Judean individuals believed about the pantheon's role in the world; however, in that text, Shamash appears as a god of justice (TAD C1.107-108).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: TAD A4.7 would suggest that god can bestow favor before the king, happiness, strength, and long life.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It seems like affiliation with YHW (over the rest of the pantheon) was a norm.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Porten speculates a line in A4.8:19 might indicate abstinence in connection with mourning rituals. I find this interpretation unlikely.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Members of the group certainly fasted as part of their mourning ritual. It is unclear whether this fasting was "required". (A4.7 and A4.8)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Cessation from wine is mentioned in connection with mourning rituals. It does not seem that this was a "required" practice (TAD A4.7). TAD A4.1 includes a prohibitive "do not drink" but the object of the sentence is missing. The letter might be connected to festival ritual but due to its fragmentary nature it is unclear. TAD A4.1 also mentions "anything leavened" beside a negative particle. One might assume the missing verb is "eat" (do not eat), but the context for this foregone food opportunity is unclear.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See note on circumcision below.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Three different types of sacrifices are mentioned in the documents- meal offerings, incense, and burnt offerings (TAD A4.7). TAD C3.15 indicates silver was also given to YHW. It is unclear who all offers sacrifices, the priests or all of the people (see A4.7:26-27 esp). (See Granerød, Dimensions of Yahwism, 129-150)

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: At least some sacrifices are burnt.

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: To YHW

Notes: The purpose of sacrifice is unclear, but A4.5 indicates sacrifices were meant to be to/for YHW

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The documents indicate prayer was a part of life in the Judean colony; however, there are few specifics on the practice. Nothing indicates it was "required." The reference in A4.7 indicates prayer was corporate, but that does not mean individual prayers were not conducted. Salutations in personal letters ("may the god(s) seek your welfare") suggest a certain type of intercession by the sender on

behalf of the recipient. (See Granerød, Dimensions of Yahwism, 154-65). The documents also suggest the concept of sabbath was present at Elephantine (although some may question whether the šbh of Egyptian Aramaic corresponds to the šbt of Hebrew). However, there is no indication that this sabbath was set apart as a day of rest (See Porten, Archives from Elephantine, 124-128).

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: There is little to suggest that the Judean community had particular ethical precepts in connection to YHW worship. The closest the documents come to this idea of ethics connected to religion is through oaths. Individuals would swear on YHW's name that they were being honest (TAD B2.12). These statements were assessed by judges. Swearing by gods was not unique to Judeans at Elephantine. There is a sense that justice might be meted out for evil, specifically the evil actions of Vidgranga (TAD A4.7). For more on ethics see Granerød, Dimensions of Yahwism, 259-323)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

— Field doesn't know

Notes: Documents from Elephantine indicate that there were rituals around mourning (wearing sackcloth and ashes, fasting, and praying) but there is nothing to indicate these were required mourning rituals (A4.7 and A4.8).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

— Field doesn't know

Notes: There are indications that Judeans in Elephantine know about PSH' or Passover (TAD D7.6, D7.24), but the documents say nothing about its practice. The date seems to not be fixed (TAD D7.6:9). The context for celebrating might have been confined to the family. (The highly fragmentary, so-called "Passover Letter" TAD A4.1 does not mention Passover).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

— Field doesn't know

Notes: One might expect circumcision to be present at Elephantine among the Judean community; however, there is no mention of the rite in documents from the group. Still, that absence in the documentation does not necessarily mean the ritual was not present. (See Becking, "Yehudite Identity in Elephantine")

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

— Yes

Notes: The term "brother" is used in letters at Elephantine to refer to members of the same group, not only kin.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

— I don't know

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

— I don't know

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

— No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

— Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Judean community at Elephantine is frequently referred to in the documents from the island "as the Judean garrison." The group primarily served a military role in Upper Egypt and the

Judeans there, according to the best information we have, were connected to the garrison. Scholars debate how to translate yhwdy'- Judean, Yehudite, or Jewish. Judean suggests a connection to Judah/Yehud; however, it is unclear whether a case can be made for a connection with Judah for every individual described by the gentilic yhwdy. Yehudite has the benefit of mimicking the Aramaic gentilic found in the document (an Anglicized derivation of the emic term) although it still might suggest a connection to Judah/Yehud. Some scholars see Jewish as anachronistic, dating the start of Judaism (in contrast to YHWH worship) to a later period. See Becking, Yehudite Identity in Elephantine; Granerod, Dimensions of Yahwism, 3n3; Van Der Toorn, Becoming Diaspora Jews, 115-142.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Letters like A2.3 seem to suggest households took care of their own who were in physical need.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The preponderance of written material suggests that there was scribal education for the community, but it is unclear who provided that education (Van Der Toorn, Becoming Diaspora Jews, 25-27).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The preponderance of written material suggests that there was scribal education for the community, but it is unclear who provided that education (Van Der Toorn, Becoming Diaspora Jews, 25-27).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There are certainly levels of leadership within the group (see answer under "does the group have official political support"). The group is also associated with a military garrison with detachments (DGL) which implies a certain structure, possibly a bureaucratic one.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group has interactions with Persian officials both in their own province and outside of their province in Judah and Samaria.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: TAD D7.39 indicates that the Persian official (satrap) was in charge of ensuring the food supply for the garrison (see also Porten, Archives from Elephantine, 59)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: TAD A4.5 indicates the group had a well that was obstructed by the priests of Khnum. No details about the well's management are given.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: TAD A4.5 indicates the group had a well that was obstructed by the priests of Khnum. No details about the well's management are given.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Large scale infrastructure belongs to the Achaemenid Empire. See Colburn, Connectivity and Communication.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: TAD C3.15 suggests the Judeans sponsored their own religious activity, but the evidence is scant.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: TAD A6.11 indicates that taxes were paid to the Persian satrap. The Arshama archive provides more details about the day-to-day economic activity overseen by the satrap.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no indication the Judeans had their own police force.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: TAD A4.5 indicates Judeans interacted with three levels of officials, police, judges and hearers, all presumably Persian officials.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence for independent Judean courts (Granerød, Dimensions of Yahwism, 47).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Several legal documents indicate that Judeans interacted with a judicial system in Elephantine (e.g. TAD A4.5, A5.2)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence of an enforcement body specific to the Judean community.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: TAD A4.3 would suggest that Judeans were subject to Persian officials' punishment.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The contracts found at Elephantine give insight into how private and some criminal law was conducted. TAD A4.3 indicates the Judean community was "under the jurisdiction of Persian officials" (Granerød, *Dimensions of Yahwism*, 47). However, it is important to note that no legal codes have been found at Elephantine.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: It does not possess one. It is part of one for another group.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The group uses Aramaic which is distinct given the prevalence of Demotic (Egyptian language) in the area; however, Aramaic was the administrative language of the Persian Empire and not particular to Judeans.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The question of calendar is complicated for the Judean community at Elephantine. It is important to not read into the documents the calendar known from the Judean community in Palestine. That said, there are references into the documents from Elephantine to Passover/Mazzot a festival known from the cultic calendar of Yahwism. The primary texts from the Judean community from Elephantine also reference Sabbath, a weekly day of rest.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Judeans at Elephantine marked their years by regnal years (in year X of King X). They used both indigenous Egyptian months as well as Babylonian months.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: TAD A5.2 indicates that the military unit might have provided food for itself.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: TAD D7 39 indicates that the Persian official (satrap) was in charge of ensuring the food supply for the garrison (see also Porten, Archives from Elephantine, 59).

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